

Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety My “Covachita”, well-being for everybody

Mariana Berenice
Alvarado De la Rosa¹
mariana@christianvivanco.com

Christian Israel Vivanco¹
christian@christianvivanco.com

¹Christian Vivanco
Design Studio, Mexico

Abstract While it can be argued that modern life has allowed us to extend the length of the average man’s life, as well as providing important benefits such as the cure of deadly diseases, we cannot forget that the vortex produced by the way of life we have achieved has diminished in several fundamental aspects of our reality.

This study seeks to generate new parameters to respond to the effects of crescent mental health problem in our society.

That is why this project seeks to flow with the times and support new generations living under the shadow of mental diseases by designing products and services that include them in society.

Keywords *Wellbeing, Behavior, Healthcare, Inclusive, Sensorial*

Introduction

This project is the result of a personal experience taken to a research in the design field. I’m an Industrial Design professor diagnosed with Generalized Anxiety Disorder and Panic Disorder thirteen years ago. This is a short paper about the process I’ve followed for these past two years with the environmental and human behavior to look forward a change in other people lives through design.

With that in my mind I put myself as a case study in order to find insights that lead me and my coworker to develop design concepts which could help people suffering (GAD) to get responses from a person who knows what mental illness segregation is. This project ends with some feedback from a small group of people with anxiety; we keep working with more information, research and validation of the concepts so once we achieve enough information we can have prototypes, this is a first approach to the project Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety. “My Covachita, well-being for everybody” which is still in progress.

Mental illness: Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD).

The human race entered the twentieth century in ignorance of what the technology developed by the Industrial Revolution represented and represents to the world and lifestyle. Scientifics began to make deeper studies on depression, anxiety and sleep disorders among others.

While now mental illness occupies a significant place in the field of medicine, in the twenty-first century it was considered a taboo. This last part builds up an ironic case in large cities because it is where many of these diseases have originated.

Anxiety is a normal response from our body to a dangerous situation. We were born like that: in

another time, when we were primitive men we used to need the anxiety alarm every time we had to survive. Nowadays anxiety is a normal part of our lives; everybody has experimented this sensation in their lives, when someone is too stressed at work, at school, in the traffic, with personal or professional problems among others. But for a person whose anxiety is becoming a “normal” part in their lives, the problem involves more than just stress; it eventually becomes a disorder and the person starts to feel anxiety in almost every part of their life and begins to loose self-control as well.

A review that pooled surveys in different countries up to 2004 found overall average prevalence estimates for any anxiety disorder of 10.6% (in the 12 months prior to assessment) and 16.6% (in lifetime prior to assessment), but that rates for individual disorders varied widely. Women had generally higher prevalence rates than men, but the magnitude of the difference varied. (Somers, Goldner, Waraich, 2006).

The problem with mental health is that it is so important that since the second half of the twentieth century there are associations dedicated to take care of people who suffer any mental disorder that make studies and research that help these people rejoin society.

The way men have been changing throughout history and the relationships between quality of life and technology development have been improved over time. “Besides the meeting place of technology and behavior, they are the link between household resources, the level of living, and the level of well-being” (Groot-Marcus, Terpstra, Steenbekkers, Butjijn, 2006).

The world is full of technology, and for better or worse, technology is with us every single minute of

our lives. This fact leads to both physical and mental illnesses and constantly to fields still unexplored by humans. Technology breakthroughs throw us into confusion when trying to define what well-being really is. This confusion results in the conception of products designed to “facilitate” people’s daily lives through the elimination of activities, rather than products designed for helping keep our mental health. “During the past decade, the role of technological objects in society and in people’s everyday lives has become a central theme in the philosophy of technology”. (Verbeek, 2006).

Generalized Anxiety Disorder in México

México is a country where it is evident that large cities can affect humans; according to the UN it has the fourth most populous city in the world. “The lifestyle of an individual actor is constructed from a series of building-blocks that relate to the sets of social practices and individual is involved in when enacting his or her daily life, together with the story-telling that goes along with it (Giddens, 1991).” Living in highly populated cities meant more traffic, a poor diet, longer work journeys to be within the competitiveness and hence implied the appearance of more physical and mental disorders.

“One in four people in Mexico has had at least one mental disorder and one in three people have had a mental disease at age 65, according to the study Psychiatric Disorders in Mexico : prevalence throughout life in a national representative sample study, published in 2007, is the latest compilation of statistical data at the population level in the country.” (Juarez, 2013).

Anxiety is along with depression one of the mental disorders that afflicts more people in the world. The Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) has been described in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders of the American Psychiatric Association (APA) is a disorder that affects millions of people worldwide, but is more common in the cities than in villages or communities.

For 10 years now, studies have been alarming; according to the National Psychiatric epidemiology Survey, coordinated by the Dra. Maria Elena Medina Mora in Mexico, and raised in 2003, the most common disorders identified in our country were anxiety (with a prevalence of 14.3% ever the lives of the people) Newspaper Excelsior, 16- July- 2013).

That is why this project tries to flow with the times and support new generations living under the shadow of mental diseases by designing products and services that include them in society. These days have an increasing need to generate designs that promote well-being to face the problems of large cities.

Today it is imperative to pay attention to our lifestyle and find alternatives to this fast-paced world; objects have always had a symbolic value, as result of the experiences that people give them. They are filled with memories and experiences and are able to function as sensory time machines, able of trigger the senses

Figure 1.

positively or negatively.

Designing for people living with Anxiety Disorder

This project aims to bring design to people who suffer and live every day with mental disorders, specifically with Generalized Anxiety Disorder (GAD) and Panic Disorder.

This project is based on three stages:

1. My Covachita: The well-being at home
2. My Covachita: The well-being outside the home
3. My Covachita: The well-being in large cities

Which is the meaning of “Covachita”?

According to the Royal Academy of the Spanish Language (RAE), Covacha is 1. f. small cave. 2. f. housing or poor, uncomfortable, dark, small room. 3. f. storage room. 4. f. doghouse. 5. f. Ec. shop where you sell groceries.

There is a particular gesture in which we tend to do “Covachita” or “house” with our hands to protect something. This project was born because of that feeling, the need to feel safe.

Anxiety Disorder tends to have various symptoms, one of them is to feel exposed; that’s why the project tried to simulate the sensation of being safe and protected regardless if you are at home, outside the home, or in a large city.

My Covachita: The well-being at home

It is a cabinet that reflects harmony, lightness, simplicity and balance (Figure 1). These values are inspired by the simple lifestyle that exists in many communities and villages around Mexico and the world. It proposes to build furniture that has significance within the home and that denotes its impact on the physical and mental well-being through shapes and materials such as wood, textiles and mud.

Figure 2.

My Covachita: The well-being outside the home

Jewelry as an area of intervention is a logical approach in this project thanks to its natural ability to be carried by men thus having direct and constant contact with their bodies and sensory attention. The second approach involved in this project is made by two pieces of jewelry, a ring and a necklace (Figure 2). This family of objects will be able to accompany the person in their transits through the city.

Both ring and necklace have storage space; the first one for carrying an emergency pill with you. Second piece, necklace will help with a natural way of relaxing which is the aromatherapy.

My Covachita: The well-being at the cities

Street furniture is designed to be part of large cities in México such as México City, Guadalajara, and

Monterrey among others, and to be present when a person needs a break (Figure 3). Today it becomes imperative to look for new ways to develop our society; this could encompass what has not been made yet in socio- cultural democratization and therefore is not reflected in the collective behavior.

Conclusions

There are several different types of anxiety disorders, nowadays most of them are treated with therapy and pharmacological treatment. There are many alternative therapies that offer help to calm the mind and help society to live a peaceful life. We have to look for options both alternative and conventional.

Objects have always had a symbolic value as result of the experiences that people give them. They are filled with memories and experiences and are able to

Figure 3.

function as a time machine that contains information that activate the senses positively or negatively.

The project: Design for people living with mental disorders: Anxiety-My "Covachita", well-being for everybody is still in process. We need more test about our proposals inside different kind of groups; this is a first step to involve design in mental health and well-being.

Human behavior plays an important role in each period framed by history. Observation, registration, evaluation and interpretation of societies constitute the basic work to understand, disseminate and show the needs and problems that must be solved through design.

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